

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

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SAMOTROVANJA ANTIDEPRESIVIMA NOVIJE GENERACIJE – KOLIKO SMO BEZBEDNI?

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Selektivni inhibitori ponovnog preuzimanja serotonina (SSRI) su lekovi sa širokim terapijskim indeksom i širokim indikacionim područjem što ih čini čestim agensom u samotrovanjima. Cilj rada je prikazati osnovne karakteristike trovanja i predoziranja SSRI, distribuciju u odnosu na pol i životno doba, učestalost pojedinih agenasa, procena težine trovanja, te uticaj koingestiranih supstanci. Retrospektivna analiza istorija bolesti 71 bolesnika hospitalizovanih zbog akutne intoksikacije sa SSRI u četvorogodišnjem periodu kod kojih je ingestirana doza leka bila veća od petostruke preporučene dnevne doze i/ili dokazane toksične koncentracija leka.

Prosečna starost bolesnika je bila 42±16 godine i većinu (60,71%) su činile žene. Trovanje je bilo recidivantno u 52% slučajeva. Najzastupljeniji agens je bio sertralina (39), potom citalopram/escitalopram (25%), fluoksetin (18%) i paroksetin (17%). Više od 90% bolesnika imalo je koingestirane druge supstance (benzodiazepini, neuroleptici, antiepileptici i alkohol). Trovanje lakog stepena (PSS 1) imalo 62%, srednje teškog 17%, teškog stepena (PSS 3) 18% bolesnika, a dva trovanja (3%) su imala letalni ishod (PSS 4). Svi bolesnici sa težim trovanjima, kao i letalnim ishodom su imali koingestirane druge supstance. Ispitivanjem odnosa koncentracija pojedinog SSRI agensa u krvi i dužine QTc intervala nije utvrđena statistička značajnost ni za jedan agens. Konvulzije su registrovane kod jednog pacijenta (citalopram). Kriterijume serotoniniskog sindroma nije imao ni jedan pacijent. Klinička slika akutnih trovanja SSRI, koja su često recidivantna, uglavnom je lakog stepena. Visoke ingestirane doze i često prisustvo drugih koingestiranih lekova i supstanci te njihove međusobne interakcije značajno utiču na težinu ispoljene kliničke slike.

KLJUČNE REČI: selektivni inhibitori ponovnog preuzimanja serotonina, akutno samotrovanje

DELIBERATE SELF-POISONINGS WITH NEW ANTIDEPRESSANTS – HOW SAFE ARE WE?

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Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), widely prescribed medications with a high therapeutic to toxicity ratio, are agents often involved in deliberate self-poisonings. The aim was to analyze the main clinical manifestations of acute SSRI poisoning, age, gender and agents distributions, overdose severity according Poisoning Severity Score (PSS), type of concomitants and its influence on clinical features. Data from medical records of 71 patients hospitalized in 4 years period with ingested doses five times higher than daily therapeutic dose and/or confirmed toxic concentration of drugs in blood were retrospectively analysed. Average age of patients was 42±16 years; most (60,71%) were female. In 52% of cases deliberate self-poisoning was repeated. The most common agent was sertraline (39%), then citalopram/escitalopram (25%), fluoxetine (18%) and paroxetine (17%).

In more than 90% of patients concomitants (benzodiazepines, neuroleptics, antiepileptics and ethanol) were presented. The PSS was 1 in 62%, 2 in 17% and 3 in 18% of patients. There were two (3%) lethal outcomes. All cases with severe clinical features and lethal outcome had concomitants ingested. Correlation between agents blood concentrations and length of QTc interval was not found for any type of agent. Seizures were registered in one patient (citalopram poisoning). Serotonin syndrome was not present in any patient. Symptoms observed following acute overdose of SSRI are typically mild. Large ingested doses, frequent presence of concomitants and their interactions contribute to the severity of clinical manifestations.

KEYWORDS: selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, deliberate self-poisonings